

Total Protein Assay Kit Instruction

(Biuret Method)

Serial No: A045-1-1 Pack: 100T/96S

1. Assay principle:

Molecules which contain 2 amino carbamoyl groups (-CONH₂) can react with alkaline copper solution to produce violet complex, this reaction is called biuret reaction. Protein molecules contain many peptide bonds (-CONH-) which are able to participate biuret reaction, different kinds of proteins appear similar chroma.

2. Reagent composition & preparation

Reagent 1: Powder× 1 bottle, can be stored at 4 °C for 6 months. When use, add distilled water until volume reaches to 100ml.

Reagent 2: Powder× 1 bottle, can be stored at 4 °C for 6 months. When use, add distilled water until volume reaches to 200ml.

Biuret reagent preparation: Dissolve Reagent 1 & Reagent 2 completely, mix sufficient to prepare biuret reagent, which can be stored at 4 °C for 3 months.(Do not mix reagent powders together before dissolving).

Protein standard: 56.3g/L, it can be stored below -20 °C for 3 months.

3. Required equipments & Reagents

- A spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 540nm
- Thermostatic water bath capable of controlling temperature at 37 °C
- Micropipets and tips
- Vortex mixer
- Desk centrifuge
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)

4. Operation procedure

(1) Sample pretreatment:

- ① **Blood serum:** Can be assayed directly.
- ② **Tissue:** Weigh tissue sample accurately, mix tissue sample with physiological saline at mass-volume ratio of 1:9 to prepare 10% tissue homogenate, centrifugate at 1000~3000 rpm for 10 minutes (different parameters need different speeds, it is about 2500rpm in general), take supernatant for assay.

(2) Operation table:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Distilled water (ml)	0.05		
Standard solution (ml)		0.05	
Samples (ml)			0.05
Biuret reagent (ml)	2.5	2.5	2.5

Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 10 minutes, cool by flowing water, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 540nm (adjust zero by distilled water).

5. Calculation

$$\text{Formula: } \begin{matrix} \text{Protein} \\ \text{concentration} \\ \text{(mg/ml)} \end{matrix} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \begin{matrix} \text{Protein standard} \\ \text{concentration} \\ \text{(mg/ml)} \end{matrix}$$

6. Announcements

This reagent can be used to assay samples of 10~80mgprot/ml, if protein content is above 80mg/ml, then please dilute sample by physiological saline to adjust protein concentration in 10~80mg. If protein concentration is below 10mg/ml, then it is suggested to use Coomassie brilliant blue kit from our Institute.